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WP6 – ACCEPT solution integration, pre-validation, roll-out

D6.8 – ACCEPT solution roll-out report

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Abbreviations

BoM	Bill of Materials
C-App	Citizen Application
IoT	Internet-of-Things
LL	Living Lab
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The current deliverable focuses on the activities carried out for the deployment of the ACCEPT solution at the four project pilot sites, i.e., the Spanish, Greek, Swiss and Dutch pilots. As not all pilot sites are currently fully equipped with the necessary Information Management Layer (be it for prosumer- or district-level information/data), the maturity of the solution rollout phase differs among the sites as well.

The Spanish and Greek pilots are the mature sites in terms of solution deployments, with the BIML component not only deployed there, but also integrated with the C-App. Users from these pilot sites will be able to access their data and visualise them through the App from May 2023 onwards. For the Swiss and Dutch pilots, the BIML and DIML components are yet to be fully deployed, so the ACCEPT solution is expected to be rolled out in summer 2023.

With regards to the two project user interfaces, i.e., the Citizen Application and the Energy Community Platform, training sessions with the end users have been carried out, followed by a short period of beta-testing, which helped gather useful feedback. The feedback is used for improving the functionalities and aesthetics of the two applications. The user manuals for both applications are presented herein.

The activities necessary for the full roll out of the ACCEPT system are presented in the deliverable in a table format for each site separately. The tables also include activities that need to be carried out in order for the demonstrations and tests to start, such as the definition of test cases and the continuous monitoring of the health of the IoT devices installed at households and the quality of the data gathered by such devices.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable

The primary aim of the current deliverable is to outline and evaluate the main activities carried out under the framework of T6.6, focusing particularly on those required for the deployment of the ACCEPT solution at the four different pilot sites.

The deployment activities cover the plans for installing, commissioning and integrating new IoT equipment with the identified existing household appliances for monitoring and managing / optimizing the operation of the latter, as well as the deployment of all back-end ACCEPT systems for achieving the project goals. The definition of the necessary IoT equipment for interfacing with existing pilot infrastructure and the respective deployment plans for the installation process of such equipment on site, as well as all the required household and installation preparations, have already been carried out under the framework of other WP6 tasks, such as Tasks 6.1 and 6.5 and described in the relevant deliverables.

The deliverable describes the process followed for training users on the front-end systems of the ACCEPT solution, namely the Citizen Application (i.e., the user interface that the household occupants will be using on their mobile phones for monitoring the performance of the system), and the Energy Community Platform used by the pilot managers for overseeing the performance of their energy community as a whole, and collecting their early feedback through a beta-testing round of the aforementioned user interfaces.

As the deliverable focuses not only on the actual deployment of the ACCEPT solution, but also around the preparation activities for such deployments, it includes the necessary documentation generated to assist with the aforementioned activities. Such documentation includes the deployment plan, specific to each of the four pilot sites, which builds on the site preparation plan presented under D6.7, and the manuals for the two user interfaces (UIs) of the project. The latter were used for training the users and familiarizing them with the main UI functionalities, in order to allow them to perform beta-testing of the tools and getting early feedback.

Finally, an early evaluation of the deployment activities, separately for each site, will be carried out and presented briefly herein.

1.2. Relation to other Tasks and Deliverables

This deliverable, which summarises the work undertaken under the scope of Task 6.6, is closely linked to the activities carried out under many of the tasks of the same work package, WP6. More specifically:

- T6.1: The task was responsible for recording the existing infrastructure at the participating households of the four energy communities, as well as defining the necessary IoT equipment necessary for the integration of the aforementioned infrastructure with the ACCEPT solution. The outcomes of the Task have fed into the deployment plan of the various pilots.
- T6.2: This is the ACCEPT solution integration task. As T6.6 discusses the deployment of the integrated ACCEPT solution at the various sites, the work carried out in T6.2 is almost a pre-requisite for the deployment activities of T6.6.
- T6.5: Task 6.6 and Deliverable 6.8 are highly dependent on the successful outcomes of Task 6.5, which focuses on the preparation of the pilot sites for the deployment of the ACCEPT solution. Once all sites have been sufficiently equipped with the right IoT devices, allowing the monitoring of the operation and the control of existing household appliances, the ACCEPT solution can safely be deployed.
- D6.7: The ACCEPT solution deployment plans provided herein were based on the site preparation plans presented in D6.7 for each energy community.

There are also dependencies among Task 6.6/D6.8 and tasks of other WPs, such as WP, WP5 and WP7. More precisely:

- T3.1: The Living Labs have been used as the main framework for the training of the users on the front-end ACCEPT systems and for gathering feedback from them after having used those systems (i.e., the Citizen App and the Energy Community Platform).
- T5.3: This task is responsible for the development of the Citizen Application, which has been beta-tested under T6.6. Under T5.3, the manual for the Citizen App has been created, reviewed and finalized.
- T5.5: This task is responsible for the development of the Vertical Energy Community Tools, among which is the Energy Community Platform, i.e., the user interface used by the pilot leaders in order to oversee

the performance of their communities. The Platform has been demonstrated to the pilot leaders and beta-tested by them under T6.6 and T3.1.

- T7.2, T7.3, T7.4 and T7.5: There is a high dependency on the outcomes of T6.6 and the demonstration Tasks of WP7, as the demonstration activities can meaningfully commence once the ACCEPT solution has been successfully deployed at the four ACCEPT energy communities.

1.3. Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable is structured around five main sections, which are briefly described below:

- Section 1: Introduction

The first section of the deliverable provides the scope and aims of the deliverable and highlights the main dependencies that exist between the deliverable (and the relevant task, i.e., Task 6.6) and other projects tasks and deliverables.

- Section 2: Deployment of ACCEPT system at the four different pilot sites

The second section of the deliverable provides details on the various activities that need to be undertaken by the consortium for the successful deployment of the ACCEPT solution at the participating energy communities and households. Building on the preparation plan for each pilot site, presented in D6.7, the section includes a timeline of all the aforementioned necessary activities for each energy community separately (as each community is at a different deployment stage).

- Section 3: Front-end ACCEPT software tools

This section of the deliverable focuses on the software tools with which the end-users will be actually interacting throughout the demonstration activities, i.e., the user interfaces of the project. In this section, the manuals for the Citizen Application and the Energy Community Platform are provided. There is also a description of the main training process followed for familiarizing the end-users with the two user interfaces, as well as the beta-testing following this training and the feedback received during the testing (and how this was used to improve the tools).

- Section 4: Evaluation of deployment activities at the pilot sites

The fourth section of the deliverable reflects on the main activities carried out within T6.6 and provides key learnings on what worked during the deployment stage, what went wrong and how this can be improved for any consequent deployments, etc. It also evaluates the effectiveness of the activities carried out based on the main goal of this task, which is the full deployment of the solution at the four pilot sites. Finally, it will highlight any pending activities for completing the deployment at the different sites.

- Section 5: Conclusions

This is the final section of the deliverable and includes a summary of the main deployment activities carried out by the consortium at the four pilot sites, the user interface testing and the main conclusions drawn from the activities carried out under T6.6 and described herein.

2. Deployment of ACCEPT system

The current section is an extension of what has already been presented in D6.7 on the preparation of the pilot sites for the deployment of the ACCEPT solution. It builds on the initial deployment plan for the definition of necessary equipment for the monitoring and control of existing household infrastructure at the various pilot sites and adds indicative milestones with regards to the rollout of the user interfaces of the project, as well as the rollout of the final integrated ACCEPT solution (user interfaces and back-end systems necessary for the implementation of the use cases). The definition of the actual tests cases which will be implemented at the various pilot sites is also considered. Tests cases are in essence the tests that will be carried out with the end users, which can combine various use cases and objectives, and consider the capabilities and specificities of each energy community and its households. Finally, in the solution deployment plans presented below, special considerations have been made for the continuous monitoring of the health of the IoT devices installed at the participating households and district assets, as well as the quality of the data collected from such devices to ensure that any optimisations are performed accurately and communication from and to appliances is established at all times in order to implement any generated optimal operational schedules.

In the below sub-sections of the current chapter, the key ACCEPT solution deployment activities are presented in a table for each pilot site, along with indicative timescales for the completion of each activity. For completeness purposes, the site preparation activities presented in D6.7 have also been included in the below tables.

2.1. Spanish pilot

Action	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30
Collection of data from pilot houses	█	█	█	█																
Review of Level 2 Audits (with HYP)				█	█	█	█													
Bill of Materials							█													
Ask for tenders							█	█												
Purchase of the Equipment								█												
Delivery of the procured equipment									█	█										
New equipment (VOC): Tenders & Purchase											█									
Installation and commissioning												█	█	█	█	█				

Action	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30
End of installation and commissioning																				
Health monitoring of IoT devices and 1st level of support																				
Citizen-App training for end-users (through LLs)																				
Energy Community Platform training for pilot leaders																				
Beta-testing of Citizen App (by households/end-users)																				
Beta-testing of Energy Community Platform (by pilot leaders)																				
Citizen App rollout																				
Energy Community Platform rollout																				
ACCEPT solution final integration																				

Action	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	
ACCEPT solution final rollout																					
Living labs																					
Definition of ACCEPT test cases (Spanish pilot)																					
ACCEPT demonstrations at Spanish pilot																					

2.2. Greek pilot

Action	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37
Collection of data from pilot houses	█																		
Review of Level 2 Audits (with HYP)		█																	
Bill of Materials			█																
Ask for tenders				█															
Purchase of the Equipment				█	█														
Delivery of the procured equipment						█													
New equipment (VOC): Tenders & Purchase																			
Installation and commissioning							█	█											
End of installation and commissioning								█											
Health monitoring of IoT devices and 1st level of support									█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

Action	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37
Citizen-App training for end-users (through LLs)																			
Energy Community Platform training for pilot leaders																			
Beta-testing of Citizen App (by households/end-users)																			
Beta-testing of Energy Community Platform (by pilot leaders)																			
Citizen App rollout																			
Energy Community Platform rollout																			
ACCEPT solution final integration																			
ACCEPT solution final rollout																			
Living labs??																			
Definition of ACCEPT test cases (Greek pilot)																			

Action	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37
ACCEPT demonstrations at the Greek pilot																			

2.3. Swiss pilot

Action	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12	M 13	M 14	M 15	M 16	M 17	M 18	M 19	M 20	M 21	M 22	M 23	M 24	M 25	M 26	M 27	M 28	M 29	M 30	M 31	M 32	M 33	M 34	M 35	M 36	M 37	M 38	M 39	M 40	
Collection of data from pilot houses	█	█	█	█																													
Review of Level 2 Audits (with HYP)				█	█																												
Development of web interface / data ingestion platform (with third party)						█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█												
Bill of Materials (BoM) for residential assets																			█	█	█												
Delivery of the procured equipment for residential assets																						█	█										
Installation and commissioning phase for																						█	█										

2.4. Dutch pilot

Action	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12	M 13	M 14	M 15	M 16	M 17	M 18	M 19	M 20	M 21	M 22	M 23	M 24	M 25	M 26	M 27	M 28	M 29	M 30	M 31	M 32	M 33	M 34	M 35	M 36	M 37	M 38	M 39	M 40	
Collection of data from pilot houses	█	█	█	█																													
Review of Level 2 Audits (with HYP)				█	█																												
Development of web interface / data ingestion platform (with third party)						█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█												
Bill of Materials (BoM) for residential assets																			█	█	█												
Delivery of the procured equipment for residential assets																					█	█											
Installation and commissioning phase for residential assets																					█	█											

D6.8 – ACCEPT SOLUTION ROLL-OUT																				
Health monitoring of IoT devices and 1st level of support																				
Definition of requirements for district assets																				
Bill of Materials (BoM) for district assets																				
Delivery of the procured equipment for district assets																				
Installation and commissioning phase for district assets																				
Citizen-App training for end-users (through LLs)																				
Energy Community Platform training for pilot leaders																				

3. Front-end ACCEPT software tools

3.1. Citizen Application manual

A Citizen Application users' manual has been developed within the activities of WP5 and in particular of T5.2, where the said application is being developed. Thus, a detailed version will be presented in the respective deliverable. i.e. Deliverable D5.6. In this deliverable a preliminary version of that users' manual has been included in the ANNEX section, that has been also circulated to the pilot end-users for preview. This manual pertains to both the web-based and the mobile version of the citizen application, providing the end-users with useful information on how to gain access, register, login and navigate through the tool.

3.2. Energy Community Platform manual

The user manual is part of the development phase for WP5 and more specifically for Task 5.5 – the manual is also presented in Deliverable D5.7, but has also been included here for completeness (especially since D5.7 is confidential and, as such, not accessible to anyone external to the project consortium and the Commission).

The full version of the user manual for the Energy Community Platform (for which the 'user' is the energy community as a whole, a role covered by the participating pilot leaders for the purposes of the ACCEPT project), the main user interface for the energy communities within the ACCEPT project, can be found in ANNEX I.

3.3. Training procedures for tool users

3.3.1. User Training – Citizen Application

Regarding the user training aspect of the citizen application, a preliminary presentation, using slides and video material of the Citizen Application tool were utilized, during the Living Labs sessions. After that, for each pilot, a focus group of end-users was selected to test the current version of the Citizen Application at the time and through a survey provide feedback. During that time, access was granted to the Citizen Application that was connected to the Smarhouse infrastructure within CERTH premises, providing a preview to the end-users of what they will see, during the demonstration activities of the project.

More information on the details on how the sessions were conducted in each pilot can be retrieved in the following pilot sections.

3.3.2. User Training – Energy Community Platform

Two separate training sessions were conducted with the pilot partners to introduce them to the application. The application was first demonstrated to the participants in each session and then access was given to them so that they could start using it themselves. This allowed users to beta-test the Energy Community Platform and provide feedback which was then used to make improvements to the user interface.

The first session took place on September 14th, 2022 and had five attendees (the pilot leaders and the project coordinator). The second session was on December the 7th, 2022 and had 12 attendees (incl. the pilot leaders, the project coordinator and SSH partners). These sessions were independent of the Living Lab (LL) workshops.

Since the second training session for the Energy Community Platform, the pilot leaders have full access to the user interface in order to visualise community-level data.

3.4. Beta-testing of tools

3.4.1. Citizen Application

After the training sessions have completed, a survey was requested to be filled-in by the participants and the feedback was collected. It included comments and suggestions by the end-users of how they consider the Citizen Application tool would be more useful to them and what might be exclude and/or included more. The collection of the feedback was conducted by SIN partners and provided for further examination to CERTH in order to start integrating it and provide a next version of this tool.

In summary, the citizen Application received mixed reviews. A good overall impression was met. Any color-coding scheme was considered good and understandable and the same applies to the layout style, that needs to be streamlined, though. However, a lack of contrast & color was considered that reduced clarity, the overall application came about as too complex and lack clarity in assisting understanding and navigation through the app, when needed. Various of these comments have been addressed so far, such as a reduced amount of information and a more simplified user interface is introduced to reduce the apparent complexity. Titles for Tabs/Pages were made more prominent (e.g. larger and more contrast in colour). Tips as pop-ups for further guidance were included to improve navigation.

In terms of functionalities, the Demand Response page was received with good reviews and the majority was content with the homepage. The topology and device consumption representation section and graph was also considered useful. However, the analytics section was considered too complex. This has been addressed by simplifying it by showing less graphs and just the ones that have been considered absolutely necessary, such as the actual consumption and its forecast counterpart, but passing out on any flexibility measure that might confuse the end-user, since the latter was considered too technical to be presented.

As of the moment of this writing, the process of integrating the received feedback is still on going. The final version of the Citizen Application, that is to be presented in deliverable D5.6, aims to have fully integrated all the comments received and more, in order to provide the end-users with their requested needs.

3.4.2. Energy Community Platform

WITSIDE invited the pilot partners to a session where they demonstrated the solution and gave them access to test it. They asked for feedback within two weeks. The feedback received was a list with the following:

Basic Measures per building and district assets

- Billing per community member
- Consumption
- Production
- Consumption rate
- Self-efficiency rate: how much of my consumption is produced by our RES & how much of my production is consumed directly by the community members compared to the total production (the rest is going to the grid)
- Price Analysis
- Demand and Generation comparisons
- Actual, Optimized and Forecasted Consumption, Production and Cost
- CO₂ Emissions
- Thermal power
- Electricity rate
- Campaigns of flexibility metrics
 - Count of signals
 - Flexibility achieved (energy and power/capacity).
 - Success rate
- Monitoring consumption on daily basis (plus access to a historic consumption data)
- Average day power usage
- Prediction scenarios as recommendations or suggestions (implicit DR), for example, if you shift your consumption from 16.00 to 18.00 you can save up to XX€/kWh

The feedback was used to improve the solution and a second demonstration was organized. The participants were requested to give their feedback again within two weeks. The feedback received was the following:

Dashboard:

- Selection of year?

Optimal vs Actual vs Optimal Operation Comparison for Cost (€) & for kWh

- Calendar: maybe would be better if you can select how you want to see the data: **daily**, weekly or **monthly**. Also, possibility to choose year. (*This comment is common to all sheets, so it won't be repeat it again*).
- Add total values for each consumption (optimal/actual/baseline) next or below the legend for the selected dates.
- Also, when moving through the days in the chart, it doesn't move smoothly and don't see the bar like it can be seen in the Dynamic Schemes for Implicit DR (see screenshot).

Days

Emissions Savings:

- Don't get the graph: what's the blue column?? Also, if as it shows here, the actual CO₂ are higher than the Baseline, there are no savings.
- Include units in the total figures.
- Also, better to show **CO₂** rather than Co2, or at least CO2.

Analytical Emission sheet:

- Include average per day considering all sources.
- When going back to visualization, it goes to the Dynamic Schemes sheet.

Flexibility Forecast (Day ahead)

- Is it for the day-ahead or a summary of the previous days?
- Can signals be sent from the Community App? I believe it could be great if Community manager could select all users (or some of them) and send an Explicit DR signal.
- We do not see the bar in the chart like in the "Optimal vs Optimal..." sheet.

Suggestions:

- Prepare a more detailed Manual for the App.
- Could it be possible to include information in the Dashboard (or a new summary sheet) from the DR activities and not only the total consumption and generation? For instance:
 - Number of DR events launch.
 - Number of satisfactory DR events (if possible to measure)
 - Energy Savings (kWh)
 - Cost Savings (€)
 - Emissions savings (CO₂)
 - % of self-generation.
 - % of self-sufficiency.

A call for clarifications regarding feedback was organized, aiming to mark all line items from the list that could be integrated to the application.

The process of the review had the following outcome/actions:

- Optimal vs Actual vs Optimal Operation Comparison for Cost (€) & for kWh sheet: We would add 3 KPIs (optimal/actual/baseline) of the total consumption next to the bar chart. Also, we have already added the scroll bar for easiest navigation.
- Emissions Savings: The combo chart in this sheet presents the amount (in gr) of Co2 Emissions (blue columns) in comparison of Actual (red line) and Optimized (yellow line) Operation measured as the amount of energy consumed in kWh on monthly time basis. The term "Savings" is the difference between the actual consumption and the baseline. It was requested to name this difference as "Savings". We would add the units in the KPIs and transform the Co2 to CO2.
- Analytical Emission CO2: We would include average emissions per day considering all sources as a KPI. The green button helps the user to navigate easier to the next analysis section, if needed it could be changed to return to the Emissions Savings sheet.
- Flexibility Forecast (Day ahead): This sheet shows the actual kWh consumed (blue line) compared with maximum (Upwards Flexibility Forecast – yellow line) and minimum (Downwards Flexibility Forecast– red line) capacity of the amount of energy a community can consume on daily time basis. Unfortunately, the signal functionality from Community App is not supported. Also, we would add the scroll bar for easiest navigation.

Regarding the filters, WITSIDE can create any date dimension needed (Year, Month, Week, Day). An updated version of the manual has already been sent and review process is in progress, aiming to finalize it within this month. Finally, it is possible to create any analysis needed if we have all the relevant fields and measures available from data providers.

An updated version of the app, which will include the above list, within this month.

4. Evaluation of deployment activities at pilot sites

4.1. Spanish Pilot

The deployment in the Spanish pilot site was finished in M26 for the 39 end-users that were going to participate in the demonstration activities, as indicated in D6.7. All households have been equipped with the necessary IoT devices, allowing real-time data to be gathered from these properties (on their total consumption, generation where applicable, consumption of appliances, ambient conditions, etc.). Unfortunately, one of the users (ACESR18) decided to leave the project due to reasons related to their personal health and also due to the visual impact that the smart devices have in their space.

Hypertech has provided access to a health monitoring tool to the pilot leaders where a quick assessment of the communication status of the devices can be done and issues can be detected on a visual way. Moreover, Hypertech has created an online monitoring document where information about the quality of data is collected and all actors involved have access in order to update it and add comments about the actions performed.

Since pilot leaders have had access to these tools, the troubleshooting protocol described in section 4 of D7.4 has been followed to solve the issues detected on the users' premises. As described there, a first level support in which the pilot manager has contacted the users have been performed, but in some cases, the second level support with a visit to the user's dwelling and support from Hypertech technical team was needed to solve the issues. Related to this second level of support, two users required extra smart meters to get info about the PV generation due to the impossibility to directly connect to the inverter App. This process will continue throughout the whole project in order to maintain all devices connected and sending quality data. Below you can find a screenshot of the health monitoring tool and the online file:

Figure 1. Health and online document for monitoring the state of the IoT devices

The main tool that will be provided to the users is the C-App, where they will have access to the information of the devices deployed at their premises and when allowed the control of those devices and also users will get information about the DR actions and the results from these activities. It is important that the users feel comfortable with this tool, for that reason a first description of the C-App was provided to 9 users during the LL last September (M21), and some preliminary reactions were collected. In order to get a more detailed feedback, interviews with a focus group consisted in 4 user were performed in M23. This task was led by SIN, and all pilot leaders collaborated in the elaboration of the survey. The results were delivered by M24 to CERTH, the C-App developer. New training sessions will be planned once the users have access to the C-App, expected in M29.

Besides the training provided by the pilot managers, new surveys/interviews to get more feedback about the beta version of the C-App will be done to the focus group. This activity, that is part of the LLs task, will be performed by an external company contacted by SIN, and it is expected to be performed once the C-App is launched.

Regarding the development of the different tools and components that need to be implemented within the ACCEPT architecture and solution, for the C-App and Energy Community Platform to be launched, the BIML is fully deployed in the Spanish pilot site, the BAM, ASE and DAM are expected to be deployed at the end of M29 while the ECTs will be ready by the end of M30. In that sense, C-App is expected to be ready at the end of M29, while the Energy Community Platform will be available by M30. Trials will start during summer 2023, which meets the timeline for the Spanish pilot where many of the loads, e.g., HVACs, are used around summertime. Further tests will be performed in Winter 2023 for DHW and HVACs with inverters.

Pilot managers will use the Energy Community Platform to get the overall results of the DR actions to be performed on their users. The main objective here is to get information about the savings (in energy and moreover in costs) obtained through these actions, and the amount of flexibility available and obtained during the demonstration activities. There have been two workshops (M21 and M24) in which WITSIDE has shown the development of the tool and pilot managers have been able to provide their feedback. Once the upgrades are implemented, the Energy Community Platform will be fundamental for the validation and the assessment of replication of the ACCEPT solution.

The final use cases to be tested in the Spanish pilot can be found in section 3 of D7.4. During the demonstration period, explicit and implicit DR signals will be sent to the smart devices and to the C-App in order to accomplish the following objectives: maximise the PV production increasing self-consumption, obtain cost savings and demonstrate the available flexibility for explicit DR. Also, P2P energy sharing and retailer optimal pricing configuration will be studied. The signals will be automatic, thus the users won't have to perform any action to activate the DR signals. Nevertheless, recommendations for users will be implemented to calculate the flexibility achieved through DR on appliances where automation can be implemented.

The following steps are:

- Continue the monitoring on the health of the devices and quality of data to perform the needed actions to keep the connectivity of the IoT devices.
- Prepare with the technical partners the demonstration activities to be performed on the pilot site (M29-M30) and start the validation during summer period to get results from HVAC devices.
- Prepare the C-App training with the support of CERTH to be delivered to project participants (M29).

4.2. Greek pilot

All the IoT equipment has been installed and commissioned in 42 residential premises in the settlement of Aspra Spitia. Real-time data are obtained from all these properties. Energy consumption data are collected from the whole house as well as from the AC split units and the DHW boiler. The users have the luxury to remotely control their DHW boiler as well as their AC units through an IR Interface. The health of the installed equipment is monitored through an online monitoring tool. All the offline issues are assessed and an action plan for each type of error is followed with the aim of resolving it.

Further installations will not be carried out. However, there is the possibility to replace a part of the already installed equipment due to faulty behavior and strange data acquisition.

The C-App has been introduced to the end-users through a Teams call. Useful feedback was collected in a Google Form. Since the C-App operates with demo-data, most the users were not keen on using it. When the C-App will be able to present the real-house data, a follow-up meeting will be carried out and a new feedback will be collected. From the pilot leader side, the Energy Community Platform is expected to be a very useful tool to understand the aggregated energy performance of the community. The platform will be even more insightful when the implementation of the Use Cases will begin and the pilot users' behavior will start to change. All the Use Case that will be deployed in the Greek pilot site are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Use Cases tested in the Greek pilot site.

ID	Name	Greek
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting	
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification	
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility	
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes	
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	
UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration	
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	

As for the readiness of the C-App the Platform, data from the BIML should be integrated. The BIML is ready while the process of integration is on-going and all the upcoming issues are resolved by the technical partners. Trails of both tools will begin at the beginning of summer 2023.

4.3. Swiss pilot

The Swiss pilot site managed by AEM is comprised of both residential and district assets in the Fondazione La Sosta (FLS) building and in the Arena Innovation Community (AIC).

In relation to residential assets, data on the electricity consumption in FLS-AEM125 and AIC-AEM104 is being collected via AEM's smart meters and stored in the company database. This data includes not only the main meter for the heat-pump based central heating system in both buildings, but also the data of each apartment (30 in the case of FLS-AEM125 and 3 in the case of AIC-AEM104). Moreover, the production of the photovoltaic system of FLS-AEM125 is being monitored.

A third-party interface for accessing this data is currently in development and expected to be completed by M28. A preliminary version of the interface was successfully tested at AEM during M27. In addition, IoT devices, such as indoor air quality sensors and electricity sub-meters, will be installed in FLS-AEM125 and AIC-AEM104 during M29 and M30. Once installed and commissioned, technical partners will have access to the data from these devices.

As for district assets, the primary focus for completing deployment is on software development, such as the development and finalisation of interfaces, APIs, and communication flows. However, in order to enable automated remote control of the temperature, a gateway must be installed in the district heating system. The installation of this device will be decided after preliminary tests will verify if manual remote control is sufficient. Furthermore, if the decision is made to install a district battery, this will require the installation and commissioning of the battery and its associated equipment.

The user testing was conducted in M24. The testing procedure involved introducing the app to the users and explaining the use of mock-up data. Afterward, users were given time to explore the functions, followed by a task-based evaluation, with feedback collected. In general, the feedback for the app was positive, with users finding the information provided to be useful. However, some users felt that the amount of data presented was overwhelming

and the app could be simpler with an easier interface. The layout and choice of colours were generally well-received, but there were some navigation issues, with users finding it difficult to navigate without guidance.

WITSIDE has shown the development of the Energy Community Platform in two occasions and pilot leaders have been able to provide their feedback. Based on the testing of the tool, the experience was overall positive, however, certain dashboards were fairly complex and not easy to understand. By addressing the concerns raised during testing and implementing changes to improve the platform's usability, WITSIDE may be able to create an intuitive and effective tool that the pilot leader can use easily in the future.

In our specific case, only AIC-AEM104 and FLS-AEM125 will have actual data transmitted to the C-App, but without the possibility of control from the users. However, this is sufficient for the rollout of the C-App, as access to the users of other pilot site (anonymized) can be provided to perform testing with additional users during the Living Lab sessions (most probably around M33).

Section 3 of D7.10 outlines the final use cases that will be tested in the Swiss pilot site. The test cases will be defined when the deployment is more advanced between M31 and M33.

4.4. Dutch pilot

The Dutch pilot site consists of the ecological neighbourhood Eva-Lanxmeer in Culemborg which was developed in the period 1995-2005 and was built in different stages.

The total number of houses participating in ACCEPT currently is 45 as mentioned in D6.7. The goal in these premises, is to obtain flexibility from the following appliances:

- PV installations
- DHW tanks and boosters (electric).

Recently, ESR received the BoM and have proceeding with ordering the IoT equipment. Once the IoT equipment is installed and commissioned, technical partners will have access to the data from selected household appliances. The process of installation is currently the main focus of ESR. Until the installation is finished, ESR cannot progress with any actual testing with real data from their pilot site.

As for district assets, the primary focus for completing deployment is on software development, such as the development and finalization of interfaces, APIs, and communication flows. However, in order to enable remote control of the temperature, smart thermostats must be installed in the households.

The main tool that will be provided to the users is the C-App, where they will have access to the information of the devices deployed at their premises and (when allowed) the control of those devices. Also, users will get information about the DR actions and the results from these activities. It is important that the users feel comfortable with this tool, for that reason a first description of the C-App was provided to a group of test users.

The first round of user testing was conducted in M24. The testing procedure involved introducing the app to the test users and explaining the use of mock-up data. Afterwards, test users were given time to explore the functions, followed by a task-based evaluation, with feedback collected. In general, the feedback for the app was that the amount of data presented was overwhelming and the app could be simpler with an easier interface. The users made also clear that they felt the app did not support them enough in daily decisions for controlling the usage of electricity. Furthermore, users felt certain dashboards were fairly complex and not easy to understand.

When a new version of the C-app will be available, first actual data from other pilot sites (anonymized) will be transmitted to the app, but without the possibility of control. However, this is sufficient for the rollout of the C-App, as access to the users of other pilot site can be provided to perform testing with additional users during the Living Lab sessions (most probably around M33).

Besides the testing coordinated by the pilot managers, new surveys/interviews to get more feedback about the beta version of the C-App will be done to the test group. This activity, that is part of the LLs task, will be performed by an external company contracted by SIN, and it is expected to be performed once the new version of the C-App is launched.

The final use cases to be tested in the Dutch pilot can be found in section 3 of D7.13. During the demonstration period, explicit and implicit DR signals will be sent to the smart devices and to the C-App in order to accomplish the following objectives: maximise the PV production increasing self-consumption, obtain cost savings and demonstrate the available flexibility for explicit DR.

5. Conclusions

The rollout of the ACCEPT solution at the four different pilot areas is largely dependent on the progress made at these pilots with regards to the deployment of the BIML and the DIML components. As most of the ACCEPT solution sub-components need the use of actual pilot site data in order to perform their functionalities accurately, they require that either the BIML (for prosumer-related data) or the DIML (for data related to district assets) components have been fully deployed. As such, the status of the solution rollout at the different pilots differs and for that reason it has been described separately.

The Spanish and Greek pilot sites, where the BIML component has been fully deployed, are the sites where the C-App will be deployed first (the deployment of the web-based and mobile versions of the C-App is scheduled in May, as the integration of the App with the BIML is already completed). The deployment of the C-App at the other two sites will take place once data from household-level and district-level assets can be obtained. The Energy Community Platform has also been rolled out to the four pilot areas, albeit with dummy data in the case of the Swiss and Dutch pilots. All other ACCEPT components are expected to be rolled out in summer 2023 for most of the pilot sites.

The two project user interfaces, namely the Citizen App and the Energy Community Platform, have been shared with the final users (in the former case, the household occupants, and in the latter case, the pilot leaders) under the framework of training sessions and the living labs. Training sessions were carried out first for both tools, followed by a period of beta-testing by the users, based on which useful feedback was received. The feedback was used for the implementation of certain improvements to the tools.

User manuals for the two tools have been created and will be shared with the users towards the end of May 2023. The manuals are presented herein. It should be noted that the manual for the C-App in particular will be translated in the local language of each pilot site to ensure maximum usage of the application by the users.

Next steps include the completion of the solution rollout, the definition of actual test cases for each pilot set, after which testing can officially start.

6. Annex I – BI User Manual

6.1. Introduction

The purpose of this section is to describe the general functionality of the Accept application in Qlik Sense. Accept application provides an overview of metrics according to energy consumption and generation per community on daily/monthly time basis to help a user to generate insights and create an action plan focus on sustainability of communities.

In the following sections, the entire process is described from when the user enters the Qlik Sense Hub, how he will open the Accept app and how he will navigate through different sheets to analyse data and generate insights using all the available features provided by the tool.

Figure 2. Process

6.1.1. Access

Using the [Qlik Cloud](#) link you are kindly requested to fill your credentials as the below figure shows.

Figure 3. Credentials page

After filling in the correct credentials, you will enter the Qlik Cloud Hub. In the cloud hub, a user can create, share, and interact with analytic apps. He can also add and interact with other's users content. This includes data sources, charts, notes, and links.

The cloud hub is divided into the following sections:

- Getting Started
- Home
- Favorites
- Catalog
- Collections
- Alerts
- Subscriptions

After your first login, you will press the "house" button as **orange arrow shows**. Home displays content that was recently updated, the apps you have access, data, charts, notes, and your favourites.

Figure 4. Enter Qlik Cloud hub and go to Home page

In order to access the Accept app, you should place on the Application window and press "Open app" green button as **yellow arrow shows** below:

Figure 5. Access the Accept app

6.1.2. App Overview

Qlik Sense is a web-based platform that has a number of different views to work from. When you open an app from the Qlik Cloud hub, the App overview is displayed. From there, you can:

- Create and edit sheets
- Apply existing bookmarks to navigate to a specific sheet with selections applied
- Work with data storytelling and apply bookmarks

The App overview displays a summary of the main components in the app (sheets, bookmarks, and stories). This is where you see and manage all the content within the app. App overview is divided into two sections:

- Navigation bar (yellow box)
- Sheets, bookmarks and stories area (blue box)

Figure 6. App Overview

Navigation bar

Navigation bar helps user to navigate in different parts of the app. In the navigation bar, you can:

- Click **Qlik** to return to the Qlik Cloud hub.
- Click **...** to return to the App overview and enable or disable Touch screen mode. Touch screen mode is enabled whenever a touch-enabled device is recognized, such as mobile phone or tablet.
- By Clicking the **Prepare** tab, you access the Data Model viewer in which user can see all the available data, structured in tables, and their associations that compose the data modelling. It is a visual representation to understand the relationships between different data elements (tables) and how they're connected so a user can better organize and manage available data.
- Under the **Analyze** tab, you navigate through the existing Sheets to analyze data and generate insights.
- Under the **Narrate** tab, you can create, edit, and play stories. Stories are small presentations that user can compose to narrate the insights and the data discoveries they have found in the app (the word insight refers when a user discovering a pattern in data or a relationship between variables that he didn't previously know existed, i.e. how a measure has changed over a certain period of time and how it has affected / been affected by another measure.). Stories can include different slides with (1) texts to explain the findings in a narrative style, (2) snapshots of the visualizations in the app, (3) shapes, images, links, and effects applied to the visualizations which highlight specific data points or areas of focus and (4) embedded sheets of the app to allow an interactive experience.

Sheets, bookmarks and stories area

In this area you can select whether to display sheets, bookmarks, or stories.

UI Item	Description
	Access to all existing sheets in the app and to create a new sheet.
	Access to all existing bookmarks in the app. Bookmarks store data selections that can be applied by users.
	Access to all existing stories in the app and to create a new story.

6.1.3. App Details

Prepare / Data Model viewer

As mentioned before, under the **Prepare** tab, you access the **Data Model viewer** in which user can see the data structure of the available data and their associations that compose the data modelling.

Figure 7. Data Model Zoom

It is a visual representation to understand the relationships between different data elements (tables) and how they're connected so a user can better organize and manage available data (available data is the data available to be used to create a report).

Figure 8. Data Model

By selecting one table, a user in **Preview** area (blue box) can view the details about the table and metadata about the tables and fields.

Figure 9. Preview area of Data Model viewer

On the right of the screen, specific tools (red box) are available to user in order to zoom in/out, search specific field or table or lock the data structure in a comprehensive way for him.

On the upper right screen there are the Data model viewer tools (green box) giving user specific capabilities:

UI item	Description
	Collapse all tables to show the table name only.
	Reduce the size of all tables to show the table name and all fields with associations to other tables.
	Expand all tables to show all fields.
	Internal table view - the Qlik Sense data model including synthetic fields.
	Source table view - the data model of the source data tables.
	Layout menu with the options Grid layout, Auto layout and Restore layout.

To learn more about Data model viewer please visit [Data Model Viewer](#)

Analyze / Sheets

As mentioned before, Qlik Sense provide a number of different ways to navigate through the different sheets in the app, either from **Analyze** tab in Navigation bar or **Sheets** tab in Sheets, bookmarks and stories area, both available in App Overview (Figure 5 **yellow** and **blue** box).

A sheet is where charts and tables for data visualization are placed. An app can include several sheets and each sheet has a purpose and provides specific KPIs and measures according to the thematical unit it analyzes, that helps user to analyze the data and generate insights. The Accept app has nine (9) sheets:

- Sheet Structure – Menu
- Dashboard
- Optimal vs Actual vs Baselined Operation Comparison for Cost Optimization (€)
- Optimal vs Actual vs Baselined Operation Consumption Comparison for Energy Efficiency (kWh)
- Emission Savings
- CO2 Emissions
- Dynamic Schemes for Implicit demand response
- Flexibility Forecast (Day Ahead)
- Demand and Generation

Each one of the sheets will be explained in detail in following sections. However, before the explanation of each sheet we will explain Toolbar and its sections.

Toolbar

Toolbar is under Navigation bar in analyze mode and provide user specific capabilities.

Figure 10. Toolbar

UI item	Description
Notes	Create, share, and collaborate on notes with others.
Insight Advisor	Search tool using natural language or request insights as well as data items. In an app you can use the Insight Advisor and perform natural language queries on the app. The search results are returned as a gallery of visualizations in which the search terms are found. Click on a visualization to go directly to the sheet it comes from or to add them to a new or an existing sheet.
	Open smart search to search in the entire data set by typing what you want to find.
	Step back in selections.
	Step forward in selections.
	Clear all selections.
	The selections tool gives an overview of every dimension and field in an app. It also gives a more detailed view of selected data, so that you can explore associations in dimensions that have not been used.
Bookmarks ▾	Create bookmarks based on selections or view the existing bookmarks. Bookmarks are made to save the work in the state in which it is presently in. Similarly, in Qlik Sense, you can create bookmarks from the bookmark icon given at the toolbar to save the current state of selections made.
Sheets ▾ < >	Click Sheets to add a new sheet, or to navigate to a sheet.
Duplicate	Click Duplicate to duplicate a public sheet and transform it. When a sheet is public in order a user to transform it should duplicate it first. Public sheets are sheets visible to any user that has access to this app with only view permissions.

To learn more about different parts of toolbar please visit [Working with notes](#), [Working with Insight Advisor](#), [Using smart search](#), [Using the selections tool](#), [Working with bookmarks](#).

6.1.4. Sheets in detail

The scope of this section is to explain in key points what is contained in each sheet of the Accept report. To access the original application please visit [Accept app](#).

Before continue to describe the sheets in details, a glossary is important to understand the concepts analyzed in the Accept application:

- Actual Operation: how the community actual operated or consumed (real scenario).
- Optimal Operation: What if the community is operated at optimal hours or consumed at optimal hours (best case scenario).
- Baseline Operation: What if the community is operated at non optimal hours or consumed at non optimal hours (worst case scenario).
- Cost optimization: Minimize cost for a specific operation or consumption.
- Energy efficiency: Is the practice of using less energy to provide the same amount of useful output from a service (such as heating water, lighting, or cooling a fridge). For example, light emitting diode (LEDs) and compact fluorescent lights (CFLs) have revolutionized energy efficiency in lighting and use far less energy for the same amount of illumination as traditional incandescent bulbs. If you switch from an old style lightbulb to a fluorescent bulb you will be producing the same amount of light, but using less energy. That is energy efficiency.
- Flexibility Forecast: It predicts on a daily basis the maximum and minimum amount of energy that a community can consume.
- Average carbon intensity: Carbon intensity is a measure of how clean our electricity is. It refers to how many grams of carbon dioxide (CO2) are released to produce a kilowatt hour (kWh) of electricity. Electricity that's generated using fossil fuels is more carbon intensive, as the process by which it's generated creates CO2 emissions. Renewable energy sources, such as wind, hydro or solar power, produce next to no CO2 emissions, so their carbon intensity value is much lower and often zero. Using electricity with a low carbon intensity value will reduce carbon emissions overall –especially if we use it during times when the largest amounts of clean electricity are being generated.

6.1.4.1. Sheet Structure - Menu

Figure 11. Sheet Structure - Menu

Sheet Structure – Menu is an introductory sheet presenting the main sheets of Accept app in buttons format that helps user to understand the key elements of the app and navigate in an easily way through them.

6.1.4.2. Dashboard

Figure 12. Dashboard

Dashboard sheet provides an overview of basic measures such as billing and consumption in KPIs and bar charts format. A calendar drill-down filter is also available, so user starting from year could be gradually led to select specific date.

Demand Vs Generation (MWh)

Figure 13. Dashboard Zoom

Bar chart shows a comparison between demand (blue columns) and generation (red columns) measures on monthly time basis. The selected community is Netherlands as an example.

6.1.4.3. Optimal vs Actual vs Baselined Operation Comparison for Cost Optimization (€)

Figure 14. Optimal vs Actual vs Baselined Operation Comparison for Cost Optimization (€)

This sheet provides a comparison between Optimal operation (blue columns), Actual operation (yellow columns) and Baseline operation (red columns) measures on daily time basis. Users can define the differences in Costs by different operations and in different dates. A calendar drill-down filter is also available, so user starting from year could be gradually led to select specific date.

6.1.4.4. Optimal vs Actual vs Baselined Operation Consumption Comparison for Energy Efficiency (kWh)

Figure 15. Optimal vs Actual vs Baselined Operation Consumption Comparison for Energy Efficiency (kWh)

Similarly, to previous sheet, this sheet also provides a comparison between Optimal consumption (blue columns), Actual consumption (yellow columns) and Baseline consumption (red columns) measures on daily time basis. Users can define the differences in kWh by different consumptions and in different dates. A calendar drill-down filter is also available, so user starting from year could be gradually led to select specific date.

6.1.4.5. Emission Savings

Emission savings sheet present the amount (in gr) of Co2 Emissions (**blue** columns) in comparison of Actual (**red** line) and Optimized (**yellow** line) Operation measured as the amount of energy consumed in kWh on monthly time basis.

Figure 16. Emissions Savings

A calendar drill-down filter is also available, so user starting from year could be gradually led to select specific date. Users can click the green button on top right to navigate and view the detailed sheet about the CO2 Emissions.

The selected community is Netherlands as an example.

6.1.4.6. CO2 Emissions

Figure 17. Co2 Emissions

Co2 Emissions sheet analyse in detail the Co2 Emissions per different factors on daily time basis. Factors are Coal (**deep blue** columns), Gas (**light blue** columns), Hydro (**green** columns), Hydro storage (**yellow** columns), Solar (**red** columns) and Wind (**purple** columns). A calendar drill-down filter is also available, so user starting from year

could be gradually led to select specific date. Users can click the green button on top left to continue the navigation in the application.

6.1.4.7. Dynamic Schemes for Implicit demand response

This sheet compares, through a bar chart, the Energy consumed measured in kWh (blue columns) with the Baseline (red line), Actual (yellow line) and Optimal (green line) Cost measured in € on daily time basis.

Figure 18. Dynamic Schemes for Implicit demand response

A calendar drill-down filter is also available, so user starting from year could be gradually lead to select specific date.

6.1.4.8. Flexibility Forecast (Day Ahead)

Figure 19. Flexibility Forecast (Day Ahead)

This sheet shows the kWh consumed (blue line) compared with maximum (Upwards Flexibility – yellow line) and minimum (Downwards Flexibility – red line) capacity of the amount of energy a community can consume on daily time basis. A calendar drill-down filter is also available, so user starting from year could be gradually led to select specific date.

The selected community is Netherlands as an example.

6.1.4.9. Demand and Generation

Figure 20. Demand and Generation

Demand and Generation sheet compare, through a bar chart, the Generation (blue bars) with the Baseline (red line), Optimal (yellow line) and Actual (green line) Demand measured as the amount of energy consumed in MWh in a Community on monthly time basis. A calendar drill-down filter is also available, so user starting from year could be gradually led to select specific date.

6.1.5. Narrate / Storytelling

As mentioned before, under the **Narrate** tab, users can compose a presentation to narrate the insights and the data discoveries they have found in the app. Stories can include different slides with:

- texts to explain the findings in a narrative style,
- snapshots of the visualizations in the app,
- shapes, images, links, and effects applied to the visualizations which highlight specific data points or areas of focus,
- embedded sheets of the app to allow an interactive experience.

Data storytelling provides a way to share your data insights, whether they belong to a larger discussion or the main topic. The purpose of data storytelling is to turn data discoveries into a story. Emphasizing important elements helps create convincing stories and supports stakeholders in decision-making.

Data storytelling lets you combine reporting, presentation, and exploratory analysis techniques to create and collaborate. You take snapshots of your discovered data to use in stories composed of slides. Snapshots can be enhanced with effects. This lets you emphasize the data insights you want your audience to focus on.

As you tell the story, you can answer questions by switching to a snapshot's source and accessing live data. This guides your story to new directions, triggering new conversations and deeper insights. Storytelling becomes interactive by inserting live data sheets in slides and making selections while presenting.

To learn more about Storytelling in Qlik Sense please visit [Using data storytelling](#), [Build your story](#).

/* There may will be some modifications in the above sheets but the functionality will not be effected*/

7. Annex II – Citizen Application Manual preview version

7.1. Introduction

7.1.1. Scope and Objectives of this document

This document serves as the User Manual of the Citizen Application (C-App), the 1st or preliminary version. A 2nd one will follow, with the finalized version of the C-App

7.2. How to reach the web-based application:

Citizen App Tool is accessible from the user by using the following address: <https://accept-capp.iti.gr>. The exact Login/Registration steps are described in the following bullets.

7.2.1. Step 1: Access the Login/Register page

To access the Login/Register page, you need to open the website or application and navigate to the Login/Register page. The web app will redirect you to this page instantly while you visit the main page.

7.2.2. Step 2: Choose between Login and Register

On the Login/Register page, you will see two options: Login and Register. If you already have an account, click on Login. If you don't have an account yet, click on Register to create a new account.

7.2.3. Step 3: Provide your credentials

If you clicked on Login, you will need to provide your credentials, such as your username and password. If you clicked on Register, you will need to provide your personal information, such as your username, email address, and password. The minimum password size is four letters/symbols. **The username information should be acquired from the pilot site and correspond to the mapping that has already occurred.** Utilising arbitrary usernames during the registration process will result in problematic registrations.

7.2.4. Step 4: Read Registration Email

An email will be sent to the email address you provided during registration to welcome you in the C-APP and provide additional information.

7.2.5. Step 5: Successfully logged in or registered

If you provided the correct credentials or completed the registration process successfully, you will be directed to the homepage or dashboard of the website or application.

7.2.6. Step 7: Logout

To logout of your account, click on the Logout button on the homepage or dashboard.

accept

Username

Username

Password:

Password

Password is required!

Remember me

LOGIN

Don't have an account? [Register](#)

Figure 21. Login Page requires username and password.

accept

Username:

Username

Email address:

Email address

Password:

Password

Password is required!

Repeat password:

Confirm Password

REGISTER

Already have an account? [Login](#)

Figure 22. Registration Page requires username email and password

7.3. Dashboard Page

Upon successfully entering the correct login credentials, the user will be directed to the "Dashboard" page, which provides access to vital information related to their energy usage and environmental conditions within the house. The dashboard displays the current Energy Flow Status, which includes both the consumption and generation of energy. Generation indicates the current generation of the household in case that a PV infrastructure exists. When the arrow points to the left, it can be translated as the household imports energy from the grid in order to satisfy the energy needs. When the generated energy is over the consumption, the arrow points to the right and indicates that the household exports energy to the grid. The middle value indicates the power flow of the household (consumption-generation). The right tab describes the total daily financial and energy balance with regard to the daily energy Prices.

Figure 23. Current Energy flow and Balance

Furthermore, the dashboard provides information related to the environmental conditions within the house, such as temperature and humidity. The colour of the measurement displayed on the dashboard indicates whether the environmental conditions stand within the preferred range. The colour green denotes acceptable comfort conditions, while red colour indicates out-of-range measurements. Only the households that are equipped with the corresponding sensor infrastructure will be able to monitor these values. Occupancy is an indicator that is extracted through the motion estimation within the household.

Figure 24. Indoor House Conditions

Devices tab illustrates some metrics about the connected devices: **Total Energy Consumption** (energy consumed since it was connected in KWh) and the **daily consumption** of the device.

Figure 25. Available Devices

Left Menu illustrates the individual pages of the web app: Monitoring, Analytics, DR EVEnts, Community & Collaboration , Notifications, Preferences and About

Figure 26. Dashboard page.

7.4. House Monitoring Panel Page

In the "House Monitoring Panel" page, the user has access to the current indoor and outdoor house conditions, such as temperature, humidity, occupancy, availability to DR programs. Additionally, devices' configuration in terms of Availability can be applied from this panel. A non-available device cannot harness the DR benefits neither to participate in any DR operation.

Figure 27. House Monitoring Panel

Information about the devices Total energy consumption and daily consumption is repeated in this tab as well.

Figure 28. Information presented per device

7.5. Analytics & Forecasting Page

Measurements about the consumption and the generation are displayed through line charts, while the wholesale prices are displayed through a bar chart. The user can select the range of the displayed measurements through the calendar.

Figure 29. Energy Flow and Recommendations

The Energy Consumption per Device tab visualizes the distribution of the energy consumption per device according to the total consumed energy in the household and provides intuition to the user about his energy consumption routines. Furthermore, a topology tab represents through a graph the connected devices in the building. The final section of this page shows estimations about the assets' consumption in time.

Figure 30. Analytics per device

7.6. Notifications Page

In the "Notifications" page, the user has access to all notification messages, while there are individual tabs for each notification category (alert, recommendation etc.)

Figure 31. Notifications page

7.7. Preferences Page

In the "Preferences" page, the user can activate/deactivate the notifications per category in order to adapt the citizen app experience to its own preferences. When the user deactivates a specific alert or recommendation category, there will be no further notification related to the selected categories. The

1. Navigate to the "Preferences" page in the C-APP by selecting the corresponding option from the main menu.
2. Review the available categories for alerts and recommendations. These may include things like Security Alerts, DR notifications, etc. To activate or deactivate notifications for a specific category, select the corresponding toggle switch next to the category name.
3. If you deactivate a specific category, you will no longer receive notifications related to that category.
4. If you wish to reactivate a category you previously deactivated, simply return to the "Preferences" page and toggle the switch back to the "On" position.

Figure 32. Notification configuration

7.8. About

In the **"About"** there is a text that informs the users about the privacy policy of the C-APP in order to provide clear and concise information on how user data is collected, used, and protected.

The **FAQ** sub-tab that includes frequently asked questions that goal is to educate the users in terms of the ACCEPT project, the C-APP and the DR activities.

Figure 33. About Page

Figure 34. FAQ Page.

7.9. Mobile application

After you have successfully registered in the Web-based application you can also use the mobile version as well. This is accessible via the QR code provided in the email after the successful register and log in in the web-based App. That is, once you have successfully registered on the web-based application, an email is to be sent regarding your status, i.e. your are successfully registered/logged-in, and in that email, a QR code is included to be scanned and give you the opportunity to download the mobile version.

7.9.1. Login and Register page

Username:
ACESR46

Password:
••••

Figure 35. Login Page of the C-App mobile version.

The procedure remains the same as in the web-based version. However, since you have successfully registered and logged-in in the web-based version, for using the mobile one, you only need to log in with your credentials.

7.9.2. Change Language

As is the case in the web-based version, the choice of changing between languages, according to the pilot site you are at, is possible:

Figure 36. C-App mobile version – Language preference

7.9.3. Menu selections

In the mobile version the dashboard selections of the web-based application are effectively demonstrated, with the user being able to select among them, via the menu button, in the upper left corner:

Figure 37. C-App mobile version – Menu selections

7.9.4. Current Status

In this menu tab the current energy status of the house is presented, with the end-user being able to identify, if his/her house is generating/consuming and how much this is.

Figure 38. C-App mobile version – Current Status tab

7.9.5. Today's Balance

In this menu tab the end-user is able to monitor the net amount of energy exchanged with the grid. In case of net consumption, the value is negative. In case of net generation, the value is positive.

Figure 39. C-App mobile version – Today's balance tab

7.9.6. Current House conditions

As in the case of the web-based app, the end-user is able to monitor the in-house ambient conditions, such as temperature, humidity, air quality, depending on the installed equipment within his/her premises.

Figure 40. C-App mobile version – Current House Conditions tab.

7.9.7. Current Energy Flow per asset/device

In this menu tab, the end-user is able to monitor the energy consumed (or even generated) per device for better management of their household consumption.

Figure 41. C-App mobile version – Current Energy Flow Per Asset/Device tab.